

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Studies on Structural, Morphological, Electrical, and Gas Sensing Properties of the Polyaniline/Manganese Dioxide (PANI/MnO₂) Composites

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Abstract

Objectives: To synthesize the pure PANI and PANI/MnO₂ composites from the reaction of aniline monomer polymerization with manganese oxide (MnO₂) particles. **Methods:** The structural, morphological, and electrical conductivity investigation of pure PANI and composites was done with powder XRD, SEM, and Impedance spectra; Ammonium persulfate was used as an oxidant. The temperature-dependent DC conductivity of samples is studied in the temperature range of 30°C to 200°C. The AC electrical conductivity of the prepared composites from impedance spectroscopy was carried out and compared with pure materials. The AC conductivity of prepared composites has been analyzed as a function of frequency. **Findings:** It has been successfully prepared by in situ polymerization. XRD results of the PANI/MnO₂ composites reveal that the crystalline structure is converted into a very less crystalline structure due to the incorporation of MnO₂ which is inside the PANI chain. The structural, morphological and conductivity of the composites remain relative to changes with respect to the weight percentage of MnO₂. The AC conductivity of composites varies depending upon a change of logarithmic frequency. On exposure to LPG gas, variation in resistance and response of the composites was observed. **Novelty:** All the samples were prepared and investigated the method of in-situ chemically polymerization mechanism.

Keywords: Manganese oxide; Polyaniline; XRD; SEM; AC; DC; Electrical properties; LPG

1 Introduction

Electrically conducting polymers described as a new class of synthetic metals reached a high interest, confirmed by the 2000 Nobel Prize for the discovery and development of conductive polymers (Heeger, 2001). Conducting polymers has become the foci of interest in materials science because of their unique electronic properties, which can be tailored. Intrinsically conducting polymers (ICP), commonly termed synthetic metals,

have been the subject of extensive theoretical and experimental studies. Among ICPs, polyaniline (PANI) has become the subject of special interest due to its relatively low cost. In the last century, PANI has been described in various forms such as aniline black, emeraldine, and nigraniline, which have been prepared either chemically or electrochemically by aniline oxidation. The most common green protonated emeraldine has conductivity on a semiconductor level of the order of 100 S cm^{-1} , many orders of magnitude higher than that of common polymers ($10^{-9} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) but lower than that of typical metal ($>10^4 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$)⁽¹⁻⁵⁾. Polymer composites containing metal oxides are extensively researched due to their unique and desirable properties⁽⁶⁾. As a typical highly conjugated conductive polymer, polyaniline (PANI) has the unique properties of ease of preparation, high environmental stability, and a special doping mechanism⁽⁷⁾. Polyaniline (PANI) is one of the most common CPs, which is environmentally stable and can be synthesized through simple and relatively cheaper methods. Room temperature dc-conductivity (σ_{dc}) of pure emeraldine salt (ES-I) form of PANI ranges within 10^{-1} to 10^2 S cm^{-1} ⁽⁸⁾, and it can be modified by several orders of magnitude through appropriate doping or incorporation of other materials⁽⁹⁾. PANI obtains various domains such as sensing applications, catalytic, and some other electrical uses⁽¹⁰⁾.

Our current research reveals notable variations in results obtained through XRD, SEM, AC, DC, and sensor analyses, as compared to findings reported by other studies. Here, we report the results of Pn and MnO_2 composite fabrication using the in-situ method. Compared to other fabrication methods, the in-situ method is obtained using the easiest methods to fabricate composites. To the best of our literature survey in the field of LPG sensors, there is no report on MnO_2 composites-based LPG sensors with 100ppm and MnO_2 50wt%. The MnO_2 composites with different wt percentages were synthesized by in-situ technique and sensing characteristics of the synthesized composite to LPG were systematically investigated.

2 Methodology

Aniline, hydrochloric acid (HCL) and ammonium persulfate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$) of analytic grade are used for synthesis of polyaniline and manganese oxide was used to prepare composites via chemical oxidative polymerization method.

2.1. Preparation of Polyaniline (PANI)

All the samples are prepared at room temperature (RT). A solution of aniline of about 0.2M was prepared and mixed with 1N of solution of hydrochloric acid at RT. The above aniline and HCL mixture was stirred for 3 hours using a magnetic stirrer. Further, the solution of ammonium persulfate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$) of about 0.25M was prepared and added to the above mixture dropwise using a pipette. Then the mixture is stirred for 8 hours at RT. The precipitate formed and separated out by filtering and washing with deionized water with acetone. The obtained final suspension was dried in the oven at 50°C for 24 hrs. The final product was ground into powder.

2.2. Preparation of PANI/ MnO_2 composite

All the samples are prepared at room temperature (RT). A solution of aniline of about 0.2M was prepared and mixed with 1N of solution of hydrochloric acid at RT. The above aniline and HCL mixture was stirred for 3 hours using a magnetic stirrer. Further, the solution of ammonium persulfate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$) of about 0.25M was prepared and added to the above mixture dropwise using a pipette. Manganese oxide (MnO_2) powder for different additive weight percentages (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%) was stirred of the final solution was continued for another 8 hours at room temperature. The precipitate formed and separated out by filtering and washed with deionized water with acetone. The obtained final suspension was dried in the oven at 50°C for 24 hrs. The final product was grinded into powder.

2.3. Preparation of pellets

Interfacial resultant PANI/ NiO Nano composite precipitates were crushed and ground well finely with acetone medium in an agate mortar–pestle. The gummed powder was then pressed to pellet form of 10 mm diameter and thickness maintained from 1 to 2 mm by applying 90 MPa pressure in a hydraulic press and dried⁽¹¹⁾.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1. X-ray diffraction:

The Powder XRD of the prepared samples was characterized using a powder X-ray diffractometer. The sample was scattered by the angle 2θ values as 10° to 80° . The Powder X-ray diffraction studies were used to describe the structure and crystalline

behavior of the PANI and PANI/MnO₂ composites. The XRD confirmation of the crystal phases of polyaniline (PANI) and PANI/MnO₂ composite samples is depicted in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively. The broad diffraction peak was observed between diffracted angle 2θ ranges from 26° - 30° which is characteristic peak polyaniline suggests the amorphous nature of the prepared PANI. The broad diffraction peak with d spacing $d=3.29$ corresponds to the reflection (200) due to the parallel and perpendicular periodicity of the polymer (PANI) and no extra diffraction peaks are observed.

All remarkable diffraction peaks corresponding to (110), (200), (310), (211), (301), (411), and (521) are diffraction planes of MnO₂. The XRD spectra of the composites confirm the presence of MnO₂ with specific peaks with small shifts compared to the standard peaks (JCPDS card PDF file no.44-0141). The shift in the XRD peaks of MnO₂ in the composite may be due occurrence of the polyaniline matrix. No peaks belonging to PANI were observed because of its amorphous nature in the composite. Previously it is reported (Vishal Chaudhar et al. 2024, Shailaja Mahadappa et al. 2022) defining the peaks of the MnO₂ and Pn. The continuation to the previous work reported it is illustrated the determination of the average crystallite size of composite especially for all the composites of weight percentage Analogous results were described for other PANI-based composites^(7,8,12-14). The crystallite size can be computed using Debye–Scherrer’s formula and the doping concentration of metal oxide is a significant parameter impacting the composite crystallinity of the composite (Gomathi et al. 2018). The average crystalline size of the PANI is estimated to be approximately 20nm (D) are calculated by using the Debye-Scherrer formula,

$$D = K\lambda/(\beta \cos\theta)$$

Where D is the average crystalline size, λ is the wavelength of the X-ray, K is the crystallite shape factor a good approximation is 0.9, β is the full width at half the maximum (FWHM) of the X-ray diffraction peak and 2θ is the Bragg’s angle (deg.).

Fig 1. XRD pattern of PANI

3.2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM):

Figure 3 shows the SEM micrographs of synthesized PANI and PANI/MnO₂ composite. As prepared sample showed morphology with randomly distributed micro-sized round-shaped particles with uniformity on the surface as well as a few agglomerations. The composite micrograph showed morphology slightly different from that of the micrograph of pure PANI suggesting the possible presence of MnO₂ distributed in the polyaniline matrix. The SEM image of PANI shows uniform morphology with a semi-crystalline-like structure and has a substantial intra-granular distance between the grains. The SEM micrographs of the composites show highly agglomerated and irregularly arranged granular in shapes under different magnifications. The grains are found to be well connected which suggests the higher binding energy between the grains. Previously reported (Omolola E. Fayemi et al.) with 1 μ m pixel with 10K magnification The average diameter of the particles was measured using Image J software considering the image known size of 5 μ m. The contrast in the image is due to the difference in spreading from a variety of surface areas as an effect of geometrical difference b/w polyaniline and dispersed oxide sample⁽¹⁵⁾.

Fig 2. XRD pattern of PANI/MnO₂ composites

Fig 3. SEM micrographs of a) pure PANI, b-f) PANI/MnO₂ composites

3.3. AC conductivity:

The polyaniline powder was thoroughly grounded in a mortar to obtain very fine particles, and then it was compressed under a pressure of (10 tones) in the form of a pellet.

The AC conductivity for the common polymer is changes with the frequency, following formula (Joshi & Sinha, 2007):

$$\sigma_{ac}(\omega) = \sigma_t - \sigma_{d\pi} = A\omega^s$$

Where (A) is a constant independent of temperature, ($\omega = 2 * \pi * f$) and (s) is the frequency exponent.

The AC conductivity of the pure PANI and PANI/MnO₂ composite as a function of frequency at room temperature is shown in Figure 4. The AC conductivity is improved with an escalation in frequency in different two regions with respective slopes. The Ac conductivity shows constant behavior around 0.6MHz and more than 0.6 MHz increases exponentially. The general values of frequency appear to be consistent with a hopping process of charge carriers (protons) between polymer chains. The ac conductivity of the composites is found to be higher compared with the AC conductivity of pure PANI. Also, the AC conductivity

decreases as the content of manganese oxide increases in the PANI matrix. Maximum conductivity is observed for 20 wt% of MnO₂ in PANI composite and the conductivity decreases for 25 wt% of MnO₂ in PANI composite. The decrease in conductivity for 25 wt% of MnO₂ in PANI composite may be attributed to the embedding of PANI in MnO₂ granules which leads to an increase in the band gap of the composite^(8,9). The AC conductivity values obtained here for the MnO₂-PANI composites is the highest when compared to similar (Manjunataha B et al. 2020) previously reported works.

Fig 4. AC conductivity PANI/MnO₂

3.4. DC Conductivity:

To investigate the charge transport mechanism in the pure PANI and PANI/MnO₂ composite, electrical conductivity as a function of temperature is studied. Figure 5 shows the temperature dependence of DC-conductivity in the temperature range 30 – 2000°C for undoped PANI and PANI/ MnO₂, which suggests the behavior of the semiconducting nature. Due to the thermally activated behavior of conducting polymers, an increase in conductivity is observed in all the composites with an increase in temperature. There may be an increase in the efficiency of charge transfer between polymer chains and MnO₂ with an increase in temperature. The dc electrical conductivity also increased as the content of MnO₂ increased in the polyaniline matrix^(1,4,16). The DC conductivity values obtained here for the MnO₂-PANI composites is the highest when compared to similar previously reported works (Rahul Jabnoor et al. 2020).

Fig 5. DC conductivity of PANI/MnO₂

3.5. Sensor property:

The gas sensing mechanism in PANI/MnO₂ composites is expected mainly because of two reasons. First, the trapping of LPG molecules in between the PANI/MnO₂ composites islands is by electrostatic forces and second is a surface controlled

phenomenon i.e., it is based on the change in surface resistance of the composites at which the LPG adsorb and reacts with pre-adsorbed oxygen molecules⁽¹⁷⁾. These sensors are based on the gas-sensitive properties of a semiconducting metal-oxide layer which is usually polycrystalline, and whose conductivity is modulated by the oxygen adsorbed at the surface and at grain boundaries⁽¹⁰⁾. These metal oxides change their conductivity in the presence of reducing or oxidising gases, such as O₂, H₂, CO, NOx, C₂H₅OH and hydrocarbons⁽¹⁾. The gas sensing behaviour of pure PANI and PANI/MnO₂ composite was studied by calculating change in the surface resistance of sensing samples with time toward LPG exposure at room temperature. In order to evaluate the gas sensing properties of composites, the electrical resistance was measured using two probe method. The electrical resistance was measured in a glass chamber with a volume of 1500 cm³. The samples are placed in sample holder of the sensing setup. Initially the air was injected into the glass chamber using flow meter in order to establish the equilibrium between oxygen adsorbed at surface of the samples and atmospheric oxygen. When the resistance of the sensor is stabilized, then the gaseous mixture LPG was injected into the chamber using flow meter and the resultant change in the electrical resistance was noted. The change electrical resistance of the PANI and PANI/ MnO₂ composite was shown in Figure 6(a). The electrical resistance found to be decreases as function of time and then stabilizes. The introduction of LPG gas toward the composite injected electrons to the pallet, and thus significantly increased the number of charge carriers in the pallet. As a result, more electrons flowed in the film and at the same time reduced the resistance of the pallet. The response of sensor was monitored in terms of the normalized resistance calculated by $Response = R_0/R_g$ and the R_g is the resistance of the sensor in presence of LPG gas and R_0 is the initial stabilized resistance of the pallet. The change in response of the PANI and PANI/ MnO₂ composite as function of time is shown in Figure 6 (b). The composites show a higher and faster response in comparison to pure PANI sensor. Hence, both these figures reveal that the response of PANI & all composite increases rapidly upon introduction of LPG gas and becomes stable within a few seconds. When compared to similar previously reported works (Pallavi T. Patil et al. 2020). Here the sensitivity of the sensor found to be higher value with a 1000ppm concentration of LPG. Also, few literature (S. L. Patil et al., 2020) found with 100ppm for NH₃ sensing.

Fig 6. a) Change in resistance of PANI & PANI/ MnO₂ composite, b) Response curve of PANI & PANI/ MnO₂ composite

4 Conclusion

This study presents an approach to synthesize pure PANI and PANI/MnO₂ composites by in situ polymerization technique, to tailor their electrical properties and sensing property. The prepared samples were well characterized by XRD, SEM, AC, DC, and sensor analyses when compared to previous reports but also highlights the novelty of our findings. The XRD spectra of the composites confirm the presence of MnO₂ with specific peaks corresponding to (110), (200), (310), (211), (301), (411), and (521). The SEM micrographs of the composites show highly agglomerated and irregularly arranged granular shapes under different magnifications. The results of AC and DC conductivity show a strong dependence on the wt% of MnO₂ in PANI. DC conductivity was found to be 1.6×10^{-3} S/m at 180°C temperature for PANI/ MnO₂ (25wt%) and that of AC conductivity was 15.80×10^{-2} S/m at 1MHz PANI/ MnO₂ (20wt%). The composite particles exhibit a better sensitivity to LPG compared with PANI. The composites show a higher and faster response in comparison to pure PANI sensors. Finally, we suggest continuing

further research to investigate in-depth into mechanisms fundamentals to discover potential uses in wide areas like materials science, electronics, and catalysis.

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